

D5.2 PoliRural Model (ed.2)

Project Acronym:	PoliRural	
Project title:	Future Oriented Collaborative Policy Development for Rural Areas and People	
Grant Agreement No.	818496	
Website:	www.polirural.eu	
Contact:	info@polirural.eu	
Version:	1.2	
Date:	7 April 2021	
Responsible Partner:	22SISTEMA	
Contributing	CKA	
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Dissemination Level:	Public	X
	Confidential - only consortium members and European Commission	
Keywords:	System dynamics, model, modules, drivers analysis,	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 818496

Revision History

Revision	Date	Author	Organization	Description
0.1	11/05/2020	Tuula Löytty	S&L	Several comments and improvements were proposed and introduced
0.2	13/05/2020	Ligita Melece	AREI	Several terms and grammatical errors were corrected
0.3	22/05/2020	Antoni Oliva	22SISTEMA	Final layout
0.4	25/09/2020	Ruth McAreavey Susanne Von Muenchhausen	REA – European Commission	General review and comments
1.0	05/03/2021	Antoni Oliva	22SISTEMA	Major review after comments from REA
1.1	15/03/2021	Armands Puzulis	AREI	Comments and improvements proposed and introduced
1.2	07/04/2021	Antoni Oilva	22SISTEMA	Document updated as per the internal reviewers' comments

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Every effort has been made to ensure that all statements and information contained herein are accurate, however the PoliRural Project Partners accept no liability for any error or omission.

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Executive Summary

Deliverable 5.1 (SDM ed.1) was a first approach to the System Dynamics Model (SDM), as part of the foresight exercise, carried out in WP5. Edition 1 of the SDM was in this sense the first iteration in a process, whose objective is to build a useful tool for guiding conversations and proposing fruitful actions. But at the same time the modules defined in SDM ed.1 are putting the boundaries of the framework for pilots.

According to the plan agreed on the General Agreement (GA), Deliverable 5.2 (SDM ed.2) was meant to be a version of the model including fine-tuned individual modules updated with secondary data and primary data obtained in T4.4.

The difference of levels in terms of foresight analysis and technical assessment needs has made difficult for the modelling exercise to begin. This is why it has been considered convenient to add simple dissemination models as a guide for the pilots to help them identify dynamics.

Deliverable 5.2 (ed.2) includes 1) an enriched version of the model, elaborated with the inputs from T4.4; 2) maps as well as working models ranging from the simplest relation to a more complex model about rural attractiveness; and 3) a guide on the process to be followed to build the models.

The Conclusion contains some reflections about the challenges in the work ahead, starting from edition 3 of the model.

1 Introduction

The first edition of the PoliRural SDM has worked as a framework to achieve the objectives of the project, and has settled the PoliRural objective 3, to “*explore the future trajectory of rural development in regions using a hybrid foresight approach (quantitative plus qualitative), taking into account both historic and current situation*”.

It can be said that the whole conceptual framework is translated in the models of the first edition (SDM ed. 1). The models were not working models but contained all the elements that may be considered around the concept of Rural Attractiveness (RA)¹.

According to the plan stated in the Grant Agreement (GA), Deliverable 5.2 is meant to be a version of the model including fine-tuned individual modules updated with secondary data and primary data obtained in T4.2 Stakeholder Mapping & Regional Panel Setup and T4.4 Needs-Policy Mapping.

To adapt the needs of the pilots some actions were taken after the first version, and so SDM ed.2 is the result of reinterpreting the needs of the pilots and also their background. So, without dismissing the framework set in SDM ed.1, current SDM ed.2 has undertaken another path, to try to accomplish both, the objectives of the project and the diverse background of the pilot areas.

SDM ed.2, hence, includes a refined version of the model ed.1 and small pieces of models, maps as well as working models, ranging from the simplest relation to a more complex model about Rural Attractiveness (RA).

The idea is to give the pilots a set of tools to help them to understand the approach and building the models with the local communities. This way, a more systematic explanation and work on the process to be followed to build the models can be given.

This process, from the foresight workshops to the final local model, is explained below. SDM ed.2 focuses on the process of building useful models with the local communities, hence a more pedagogic approach is developed here.

Keeping this in mind, edition 2 consists of three blocks:

- **A refined version of ed.1 model**, having incorporated inputs from WP4.
- **A complete guide of steps** starting in the foresight workshops, to be able to build the working models reflecting local dynamics with the support of the SD experts.
- **A set of models** acting as guides and examples, from very simple sample models relating two or three variables, to the more complex ones, explaining concepts as Rural Attractiveness.

¹ D5.1 PoliRural Model (ed.1), contained 8 modules or maps: Population Model; PostSchool Will; Working Age and Elderly Will; Land Use; Agriculture and Agricultural Production; Infrastructures / Quality of Life; Territorial Capital; and Rural Employment.

2 Description of PoliRural Model 2

The model is described below, with the following points: in 2.1 there is a description of the inputs coming from WP4 and the foresight exercise; 2.2 contains an enumeration of the main modifications introduced; and finally, 2.3 is a description of the eight modules, focusing on the improvements compared to edition 1.

2.1 Inputs from WP4 and foresight exercise

Some of the inputs from pilots, gathered from documentation in WP4 (D4.2 and D4.4), and in WP5 foresight activities, gathered in the document *The POLIRURAL Compendium of Foresight Initiatives for Rural Regions* elaborated by Patrick Crehan (CKA) were considered.

Inputs were classified in four blocks: Land and Environment, Agriculture, Society and Economic Development. See below how the model has been modified considering inputs in the different blocks.

2.1.1 Land and Environment

- **Land Management and Rural Planning**

Actions defined under this title will impact Agriculture, Natural Capital and Quality of Life modules, in the way specified below.

- AGRICULTURE:

Fix a value for maximum agricultural land (*max agricultural land*).

Define and give a value to the index of multifunctionality (*diversification/multifunctionality*).

- NATURAL CAPITAL:

Define Natural Capital as hectares relative

Fix the value of natural land.

- QUALITY OF LIFE:

Predict citizens' needs and improve the accessibility variables (health centres, VT, University, city and regional connections and community activity).

- **Balance between artificial and natural land**

Variable *natural capital net variation* in NATURAL CAPITAL module reflects this balance.

- **Landscape and heritage**

Landscape quality and cultural heritage increases the value of Natural Capital. To reflect this, a new variable has been introduced in NATURAL CAPITAL module, *landscape and heritage preservation*.

- **Biodiversity**
The effects of biodiversity are introduced via *CAP Eco-Schemes* and its *effect of agriculture on Natural Capital*.
- **Energy**
New means of energy production can be introduced in the model through the *creation of primary jobs*. This variable is also affected by the *Natural Capital* stock, in NATURAL CAPITAL module.

2.1.2 Agriculture

- **Innovation**
The effect of innovation in agriculture is here expressed in two ways, always related to CAP reform as the tool to introduce innovations and improvements. The first one is in the relation *CAP effect on agriculture profitability – agriculture profitability*. The second one is through the Agriculture Knowledge Innovation System (AKIS), introduced by the CAP reform. AKIS is supposed to affect not only profitability, but also jobs in services and industry, as reflected in AGRICULTURE module.
- **New farmers**
The entrance of new farmers is treated twofold: in the *generational transition ratio* to substitute retired farmers; and all the way from *potential new farms* to *increasing farms*.
- **Financial security of farmers**
This subject is observed partially in two variables: *agriculture profitability* and *farming attraction factor*.
- **Sustainable agriculture**
The variable *diversification / multifunctionality* is where sustainable agriculture should be introduced. This will affect stock of natural capital in the correspondent module.
- **Agricultural diversification and industry**
The subject is covered by *related agricultural jobs effect on industry* and also in *diversification / multifunctionality*. The first one can be stimulated by AKIS and farm to fork strategy, included in the CAP reform.
- **Modernization of the agri-food system**
Modernizing the agri-food system will affect *agriculture profitability* and *related agricultural jobs effect on industry*. The latest can be done through AKIS tool from CAP reform.
- **CAP reform and Green Deal**
CAP reform has been covered through instruments such as Eco-Schemes and AKIS, and their effects on employment in services and industry. CAP reform it is also expected to improve *agriculture profitability* variable.

2.1.3 Society

- **Social inclusion**
Inclusion it is considered a component of the *social capital* variable. It may include concepts as elderly inclusion, fight against poverty, women inclusion, etcetera. In places where newcomers are important or a challenge for the future, their inclusion and the relations between them and traditional inhabitants shall also be covered here.
- **Public transport and services accessibility**
QUALITY OF LIFE module contains the stock *mobility infrastructures per person*. The stock is responsible for accessibility of health centres, VT centres and University. It also affects *city and regional connection access* and *community activity and networks*.
- **Depopulation**
Depopulation is one of the main dynamics affecting many rural areas. POPULATION module deals with possible depopulation trends and its effects in the rest of the model.
- **Quality of life**
The module QUALITY OF LIFE covers many aspects of the term. However, a specific indicator can be obtained combining the different variables of the module.
- **Pride and identity**
Social capital, combining with *community activity and networks* and *shared knowledge* cover the sense of identity and belonging.
- **Housing**
Housing accessibility is a factor considered in attraction and retention. For the moment is considered an exogenous variable, to be assessed by the pilots. Housing accessibility is introduced in RURAL ATTRACTIVENESS and RURAL RETENTION CAPACITY modules (see point 2.3).

2.1.4 Economic Development

- **Enterprise development and job creation**
Job creation is tackled together with entrepreneurship and SMEs growth. They are all considered new initiatives. They are first considered potential initiatives, then implemented and finally stablished jobs. The stream of initiatives creation depends on *social innovation*, *institutional support* and *pressure to take risk* (based on passed history), all defined in QUALITY OF LIFE module.
The development of particular sectors (green economy, knowledge based economy or others) will be covered by the circuit specified above. In some cases, they may be also spurred by other factors such as AKIS, Eco-Schemes or the stock of Natural Capital (the later in the case of tourism and primary sector).
In the case of agriculture, new jobs come from the *retirement substitution* as well as the creation of new farms, a function of *land access* and *farming attraction factor*.

- **Economic diversification**

Depending on the definition, scope and objectives, an indicator of economic diversification can be obtained by comparing *total regional employment* with the jobs in the different sectors.

- **Remote workers**

Endogenously, remote workers can be attracted via *broadband infrastructure*. The rest of actions will be exogenous and can be incorporated in the remote workers evolution over time.

2.2 Model modifications

Several modifications were made, some of them responding to improvements needed to better reflect identified dynamics or to gain consistency and internal coherence.

Apart from the improvements in content, edition 2 also represents a further step in the evolution from a map to a working model. In this sense modifications include:

- Consistency: although no formulas were yet introduced a unit check was done, to strengthen consistency of the model.
- Population services: a variable linking population and a portion of service jobs was introduced, referring to basic services and needs.
- Agriculture: basic stock of Agriculture module switched from Agriculture Land to Farms. The reason for the switch is to better address issues like retirement, profitability or CAP reform.
- Natural capital: the unit for this stock is considered to be *ha equivalent* thus allowing other concepts beyond Natural Land (e.g., *labour intensity of agriculture* and *Eco-Schemes*).
- New Modules: two new modules were added to the existing six. These are Rural Attractiveness and Rural Retention Capacity. As it will be explained in the next point, these modules gather information from the rest and structure the decision of moving rural (for newcomers, in Rural Attractiveness) or staying rural (for local residents, in Rural Retention Capacity).

2.3 Description of modules

The following is a brief description of modules, focusing on the improvements and additions in relation with edition 1. As it has been said, a module is a part of the model in which some aspect is detailed. All modules are connected by one or more variables, and the only purpose of separation is to facilitate understanding. The general structure of modules and their interaction can be seen in the figure below.

The model contains two new modules: RURAL ATTRACTIVENESS and RURAL RETENTION CAPACITY. Both are complementary to the Population module, for they define the decision to stay (RURAL RETENTION) or move rural (RURAL ATTRACTIVENESS) and quantify the total net flow for every age cohort, as explained below.

Figure 1 Modules structure

2.3.1 POPULATION

No major changes in the POPULATION module. The aging chain structure is still the base. Minor changes in the names of some variables or the approach (e.g., *mortality rate* has been turned into *life expectancy*).

Key driver are still rural attractiveness and rural retention capacity, and these are affecting flows in and out in the different age groups.

2.3.2 EMPLOYMENT

Employment module keeps its structure in four stocks representing jobs in agriculture, rest of primary sector, industry and services. However, a new stock representing *population services* has been detached from the rest of services, so that it reflects the services directly related to the number of people leaving in the area, as shown below.

The image shows the structure of growth or degrowth of the stock. By comparing rural population in two intervals the difference is obtained. When the difference is positive, population services will be created, and they will be destroyed when population shrinks.

Figure 2 Population Services detail

As explained D5.1, the module is still a simplification of the local economy, with the assumption that jobs are an indicator of the economic activity. For more profitability and revenue, more jobs will be created.

Employment gap, obtained by comparing total regional employment and effective workforce, is the main influence in the net migration ratio for young people and working age population.

2.3.3 AGRICULTURE

As explained above, agriculture module centre has changed from the stock *agricultural land* to *farms*. This change in the approach has allowed the module to introduce important variables related directly to the farming operation: retirement (covered and not covered), abandonment for profitability issues. Some other variables linked to the agriculture activity are now referred to the unit farm: average jobs per farm or jobs on industry or services related to the agriculture sector are some examples.

The image below shows the basic structure of the module around farm stock.

Figure 3 Agriculture Module around Farms stock

2.3.4 EDUCATION

Education module keeps the same structure as in edition 1, with the triple aging chain considering unskilled workers, vocational training students and professionals, and University students and professionals.

The only change is the addition of a feedback loop linking workforce specialization and AKIS (Agriculture Knowledge Innovation System) strength. AKIS is an important asset of the CAP reform and it has a local character and impact. The addition reflects the importance of the feedback that can be built between AKIS strength and workforce specialization: the more specialization, the stronger will be the AKIS, and the more specialization will stir again. The loop is shown in the image below.

Figure 4 AKIS feedback loop in Education module

2.3.5 NATURAL CAPITAL

Natural Capital is still considered a stock, as it was in edition 1. However, some additions have been introduced in edition 2, related to the effect of the agriculture and landscape and heritage preservation.

Agriculture is considered to affect Natural Capital in two ways. The first one linked to diversification and multifunctionality. A diversified farm is considered to increase Natural Capital, while a highly specialized and monofunctional farm will decrease it.

The second one deals with the efficiency of the Eco-Schemes applied (Eco-Schemes are introduced in the CAP reform, they are nationally defined, and they constitute a tool to improve biodiversity and ecosystems health); and also the labour intensity of agriculture (measured in jobs per ha). The later gives an idea of the type of agriculture and the impact it may have in the environment. Those two are gathered in a single index which impacts on the natural capital net variation.

Figure 5 Natural Capital module structure

2.3.6 QUALITY OF LIFE

Quality of life is a very broad and complex concept, but also a crucial aspect of rural attractiveness. In order to simplify and make the term operative, the module includes three components: infrastructure; social capital; and entrepreneurship. Thus, the structure of PoliRural SDM ed.1 has been reproduced.

The module maintains the same structure with only small additions. Shared knowledge is considered to be influenced by the relative population change: a stable population will have stronger community practices and shared knowledge.

The second addition refers to the flow *creating potential initiatives* which is now considered a ratio of the total *Working Age Population*.

2.3.7 RURAL ATTRACTIVENESS

The module of Rural Attractiveness gathers the main factors considered when deciding to move to a rural area. The factors are considered different for young people, working age population and elderly as well as the weights given to every factor.

Employment is the decision driver in young people and working age population groups. In such cases the rest of the factors are only refining the decision process. In other words, when there is employment population in these groups will be considering moving, and then the factors take part in the decision process. When there is no employment perspective the attractiveness will be considered zero.

In the following table find the factors considered for the different age groups (weights are introduced by pilots).

	YOUNG POPULATION	WORKING AGE POPULATION	ELDERLY POPULATION
Housing accessibility	weight	weight	weight
Natural capital	weight	weight	weight
Cultural appeal		weight	weight
Medical and care services			weight

Table 1 Factors and weights for Rural Attractiveness

These factors, as well as the ones considered in the next point, come from the considerations arisen in WP1 and WP4 (see D4.2), as well as conversations with pilots and bibliographical references collected all in D5.1. However, these factors may also be modified by pilots if they consider some others are more important to define Rural Attractiveness and Rural Retention Capacity.

2.3.8 RURAL RETENTION CAPACITY

This module gathers the information and decision process for rural inhabitants to stay or leave rural areas. The structure follows the one in the previous module, but with some differences in the way factors are considered.

Employment is considered the main factor (with the higher weight), but not the driver of decision in young people. They will consider employment together with the rest of factors. However, for the working age group employment will be the driver then refined by the rest of factors, as it was the case in the previous module.

The factors considered here are not the same as in Rural Attractiveness. This is due to the fact that local inhabitants considered different things when deciding to stay or leave home.

It has to be stressed though, that pilots will be able to modify the factors considered in each case.

	YOUNG POPULATION	WORKING AGE POPULATION	ELDERLY POPULATION
Higher education accessibility	weight		
Housing accessibility	weight		
Employment	weight	condition	
Broadband coverage	weight	weight	
Social capital	weight	weight	weight
City and regional connections		weight	
Medical and care services			weight

Table 2 Factors and weights for Rural Retention Capacity

3 Pilots' Model Building Process

To get the pilot teams introduced to the modelling process they will be guided through four phases. The process is a derivative from the general foresight exercise, so that some of the methods come at their time from there. The four phases are explained below, and are the following:

- Drivers Analysis
- Building the Matrix KPI – DRIVERS
- The High-Level Model
- System Dynamics Experts' Layer

The last two phases are iterative, so the high-level model may be modified and so does the SD Experts' Layer, as shown below.

Figure 6 Model Building Process Scheme

3.1 Drivers Analysis

As described by P. Crehan (CKA) at the working document for pilots, *“DRIVERS ANALYSIS is a process whereby you obtain an overview of the factors that are driving change in your region, with a view to understanding the challenges faced and how they are likely to evolve in the coming years.”*

The challenge here is to link the approach and the outputs of the analysis with the modelling exercise from the beginning.

Some considerations heading at the challenge:

- SDM ed. 2 modules and maps should be considered as a framework for the analysis.
- Also consider the definition of Rural Attractiveness designed in WP1 PoliRural Framework (D1.1 Envisioning More Attractive Rural Places & Professions).
- In terms of SDM, the main dynamics are POPULATION, SOCIAL INNOVATION, NATURAL CAPITAL and KNOWLEDGE.
- Factors driving changes will impact on the KPIs. This can be used as a general statement and a rule for the first maps, although final relation in the model will not be often linear or straight, but indirect.
- Policy options may be considered as drivers.

Final output of the drivers' analysis will include:

- A complete list of KPIs
- A complete list of drivers (enablers and barriers)
- A series of short narratives explaining how and why these factors will influence the KPIs

The narratives are very important since they will constitute the base of the dynamics in the model.

It is also important to make the distinction between endogenous and exogenous variables. For the distinction consider the former as the ones over which you can have control, and the latter the ones over which you don't have control.

3.2 Building the matrix KPI – DRIVERS

The matrix KPI – Drivers relates both in a table. If the list of KPIs is too long or covering too many sectors, it is better to focus on two or three of them, following priorities decided by the group. Once we have the list of KPIs and Drivers, the matrix can be built.

In the point where a driver and a KPI cross, a brief narrative explaining how both are related is placed.

In the table below, an example of a matrix in the tourism sectors, with four KPIs and seven drivers to be considered.

	KPI 1: No. of Visitors to the region	KPI 2: No of Nights spent in the region	KPI 3: Spending by visitors to the region	KPI 4: Jobs created in the region
D1: Infrastructure	Dynamic explaining how Driver D1 affects KPI 1			
D2: Hotels and accomodation				
D3: Sites, monuments and museums				
D4: Events				
D5: Entrepreneurial Ventures				
D6: Skills				
D7: Visibility and Awareness				

Table 3 A sample matrix KPI - Drivers

3.3 The High-Level Model

The completed matrix leads to the high-level model. This model is meant to be a very intuitive construction relating drivers and KPIs. It can be built up of small pieces or just in bigger ones, containing more than one relation.

This first relation may be enriched with general dynamics explaining the local situation. It can be of interest to consider the archetypes to identify possible dynamics taking place in the area. Archetypes are patterns of behaviour so common in organizations and broader social systems, that they have predictable consequences and well-understood solutions.

Many chronic, complex problems can be viewed through the lens of systems archetypes. Therefore, knowing the basic stories and systems archetypes gives us initial insights into many of the local issues².

In the following table there is a list of some of the most common archetypes to consider when modelling social systems³.

² Stroh, David Peter (2015). Systems Thinking For Social Change. Chelsea Green Publishing

³ Senge, Peter M. (1990).The Fifth Discipline. Currency Doubleday

NAME	DESCRIPTION	DIAGRAM
<p>Limits to growth</p>	<p>A dynamic of growth begins to slow and eventually comes to a halt and may even reverse and begin to accelerate and collapse.</p>	
<p>Shifting the burden</p>	<p>A short-term solution is used to correct a problem with apparently immediate results. This correction implies more fundamental long-term corrective measures are used less and less. Over time, the capabilities for the fundamental solution may atrophy leading to even greater reliance on the symptomatic solution.</p>	
<p>Eroding goals</p>	<p>A particular case of 'Shifting the burden' in which the short-term solution involves letting a long-term goal decline.</p>	
<p>Success to the successful</p>	<p>Two activities compete for limited resources. The more successful one becomes, the more support it gains, thereby starving the other.</p>	

Table 4 Archetypes diagrams

The final output will be a set of direct relations between drivers and KPIs. These relations can be either one to one or grouped in small sets, and they can be expressed in the most intuitive way, without a System Dynamics appearance or language. They can also be completed with identified dynamics (archetypes or any other dynamic), also expressed in non-technical but plain language. Some examples of the outputs can be found below.

Figure 7 Some examples of expected outputs

3.4 SD experts' layer

From the High-Level Model it is possible to evolve to the SD experts' layer. This step consists in building a real (in terms of SD techniques) and working model taking as the base of work, the one built by the local community in chapter 3.3.

This step has to be done by SD experts, but any of the changes adopted will be explained to the community, so that they can understand the reasons and the sense of the improvements. High-Level Model and SD experts' layer 3.4 are improved in an iterative process.

As a result of the whole process, a working model will be obtained, ready to introduce data and do the calibrations needed to make it reliable and robust.

4 The set of guiding models

As the third part of the SDM ed.2 a set of models and maps have been created. They all have training and guiding purposes, and they are not based on any real area.

They include a model for the SDM (4.1) series of maps, two very simple models relating two simple variables with no feedback (4.2), and a more complex model focusing on Rural Attractiveness (4.3). From the simplest to the more complex model, the idea is to give a tour in the process of construction of an operational model for the pilots.

All three models are available in the Exchange ISEE Systems platform⁴.

4.1 System Dynamics Model Seminar

<https://exchange.iseesystems.com/public/antoni/polirural-madrid-map/index.html#page1>

This model was built for support in the seminar that was held during the General Assembly of the PoliRural project, January 2020 in Madrid. The model contains three maps (figure 3, 4 and 5) showing concepts and variables affecting rural attractiveness, farm net income and economic diversification.

The intention was to show in the form of SD maps, ideas and concepts related to the three subjects mentioned, to get the pilots to think in their particular cases and identify KPI, drivers and optimally dynamics taking place.

Figure 8 Rural Attractiveness map

⁴ Exchange is the ISEE Stella platform to share models online. It can be reached in <https://exchange.iseesystems.com/>.

Figure 9 Farm Net Income Map

Figure 10 Economic Activity Diversification

4.2 A set of small simple models linking variables in the field of tourism

In order to see the effect of a simple relation between two variables, two simple models were designed and built, both of them in the field of tourism, as an example. The first one about the effect of infrastructures in the number of visitors. The second one about the nights spent by visitors and the accommodation sites.

- Visitors and airport capacity

A piece of a tourism model to understand the relation of infrastructures capacity and the number of visitors by air.

<https://exchange.iseesystems.com/public/antoni/visitors-by-air/index.html>

The model considers a first enlargement of the airport in 2007, and a second one to be decided. According to the year and the capacity projected, an increase in the number of visitors will be achieved, after the structure shown below.

Figure 11 Effect of Infrastructure on the number of visitors

The graph shown in the interface included three prebuilt scenarios as well as real data for a given airport (in this case in Albania). The trend drawn by the real data matches the one projected by the model, so that the model is explaining quite well what really happened, and thus may be used to do some projections and see future evolution of the trends.

Figure 12 Visitors by air with real data and 4 scenarios

By introducing new values of the variable ‘adding extra capacity’ along the years it is possible to see the impact in the output ‘arrival of visitors by air’ and compare it with the prebuilt scenarios.

This model has also been adapted to an ISEE Player’s version. ISEE player is a reader that allows running the model and build scenarios without need of the web interface.

- **Accommodation Sites and total nights spent by visitors per year**

Another piece of the tourism model linking accommodation sites, average use of beds per year and yearly visitors.

<https://exchange.iseesystems.com/public/antoni/nights-spent-per-year-v2/index.html#page1>

Figure 13 Structure and Graph for the relation Night Spent – Accommodation Sites

The model includes a baseline scenario considering a final goal in the number of sites and a year for the objective to be reached. It also includes real data from Albania. The user may elaborate new scenarios by changing variables ‘accommodation sites objective’ and ‘year to reach objective’.

4.3 Polirural Sample Model Population with Rural Attractiveness

<https://exchange.iseesystems.com/public/antoni/polirural-sample-model-population-with-rural-attractiveness-february-2020/index.html#page1>

This is a sample model that considers Rural Attractiveness (RA) as the main factor regulating urban/rural population flows, in both senses (from rural to urban and the other way around).

In the example Rural Attractiveness is defined by two factors: the **perception of natural capital** and the **relative cost of living** (comparing cities and rural areas). Every one of these factors has a weight in the final definition of RA, and it can be regulated in the interface.

At the same time Rural Attractiveness is affecting three key variables:

- **Employment:** only with a certain level of RA, rural areas will attract people to work there; then RA will be regulating the flow from potential employment to real employment in rural areas.
- **Commuters:** RA will define the proportion of urban employed people longing to move to rural areas and commute every day to work.

- **Migration:** RA is also defining the proportion of people moving from rural areas to cities.

Figure 14 Structure of the sample model Rural Attractiveness - Population

An interface has been created on which you can adjust variables and see the results. Find below the meaning and scope of the variables.

- **Potential Population Ratio Moving:** Proportion of potential people willing to leave rural areas. It goes from 0 to 30% of the present rural population.
- **Rural Attractiveness Threshold to Move:** what is the value of Rural Attractiveness at which rural population will decide to move? You can vary the RA threshold from 0 to 0,6.
- **Potential Population Commuting:** Proportion of regional population willing to commute for a given RA value. It goes from 0 to 10% of the total regional population.
- **Rural Attractiveness Threshold to Commute:** what is the value of Rural Attractiveness at which commuters will decide to live in rural areas? Again, you can vary RA threshold from 0 to 0,6.

5 Conclusion

PoliRural Model ed.1 is the conceptual and operational framework for the modelling exercise. The aim of the first version of the model is to build a framework for the pilots to understand the approach of SDM and to think in their own specificities, starting from the general model drawn. In this sense the model is a good point of departure.

In this sense, edition 2 is a further step in this direction. The model has been refined considering inputs from partners (mainly pilots but also from working papers from WP1 and WP5) and it also contains major improvements, and it is ready to become operative in the third version.

But it is also important to note that SDM ed.2 incorporates a set of tools including a guide to build simple models step by step, as well as sample models with different complexity levels.

From the approach of the project, the present edition also represents a clearer adaptation into the foresight exercise, where the model is meant to fit. In this regard, it is a key aspect to describe the process from the initial drivers' workshop to the final experts' layer from the point of view of the model.

Several webinars took place to explain the guide and the sample model.

Main challenges ahead are to:

- put all the pieces together in order to get the 3rd edition of the model, with the data obtained in WP4 and the direct interaction with pilots;
- work on a user-friendly interface that makes the model a useful tool to support foresight;
- define very clearly the process to be followed by pilots to get the most of the SDM.

To cope with these challenges, a collaborative work with the pilots is needed. Putting all the pieces together is more complicated than just drawing them in the same model: an integration work must be done, and it must be done in common, SD and local experts working side by side.

Figure 16 EDUCATION module

Figure 17 EMPLOYMENT module

Figure 18 NATURAL CAPITAL module

Figure 19 POPULATION module

Figure 20 QUALITY OF LIFE module

Annex II Responses to the monitors' comments

Comment made by the monitors	Explanation
<p>There is a lot of technical detail but in the end it is not clear how this will be useful at the local level. What is the historic data that will be used? How does this correlate to other data in the project?</p>	<p>SDM is considered a support tool for the foresight exercise, and this is the aim of WP5. At the level of ed.2 it wasn't found necessary going into the details of historic data yet (although it has been said in the workshops the period will be 2010 – 2040).</p>
<p>The work tends to be disconnected from WP4.</p>	<p>D5.2 is not disconnected from WP4, but rather waiting for its results, as it is written in the document. However, draft documents from WP4 as well as insights from partners contributed to the refinement of the model.</p>
<p>As a guide to build the models this deliverable is lacking in specific instruction as to how to do this, especially for those with little experience of the process. It is rather abstract and does not take account of existing strategies and documents as well as expertise that can feed into the process.</p>	<p>The main idea of D5.2 was to go one step further in the construction of the model, and the structure responds to this objective. It was also found interesting to add information related with the workshops and how the model will fit in the foresight exercise. However, we do not expect the pilots to build their own models, for this is out of scope in the present project.</p>
<p>It is notable that population/demography is not identified as a dynamic within the pilot areas (p. 7). PA 6 does not fully fit with D5.2 since Rural Attractiveness is put in the centre (see WP1) while the model more focuses on the three pillars 'Population, 'Land Use' and 'Agriculture'.</p>	<p>Population/Demography it is considered as a principal dynamic, contrary to what is said in the review report. New Modules have been introduced: Quality of Life, Natural Capital, Rural Attractiveness and Rural Retention Capacity. The latter two gather information from the rest of modules to build combined ratios of attractiveness and retention capacity.</p>